

Exposing available distance relay operations near high wind penetration

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1. Abstract

Commonly, Distance protection function and its settings are designed for grids largely dominated by synchronous generators. Nevertheless, today's renewable generator farms such as; photovoltaic systems, Type 3 and Type 4 wind turbines are interconnected to the grid through partial or full-scale power electronic (PE) voltage source converters (VSC). They have the capability of fast switching in order to control their output power if necessary during an event. The control strategy and the electric circuit are substantially important in the short-circuit current characteristic in PE-based generators, In fact, it differs significantly from the conventional synchronous generators behavior which do not use PE interfaces. This paper examines the performance of the distance protection function in four different brand commercial relays in a Hardware in the Loop (HiL) environment with diverse type of faults and scenarios. The tests reveal the strengths and weaknesses of the relays. The results shown in this paper can be used as an overview of the actual protection devices performance in the present and forthcoming scenarios. The work is part of the EU project MIGRATE dealing with Massive Integration of Power Electronic Equipment.

Keywords: Distance protection, Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG), renewable energy generators (REGs), MIGRATE

2. Introduction

The wind farms are increasingly integrated to the grids at different levels of voltage across the world. The share of such farms in a power system is also rising day by day. The difficulty that arises in integrating such farms is primarily due to uncontrollable wind speed. The frequency and voltage fluctuations, due to speed variation, have been solved to a greater extent by power electronics-based control arrangement provided in each generating unit of a farm. The speed variation also results in fluctuating output power throughout a day. The output power of a generating unit has a nonlinear relationship with the wind speed, and when the speed is beyond the limits, the farm cannot contribute to the grid. Due to under or over voltage conditions, a group of turbines may trip while others may remain in operation. The transmission system that connects such farms will be exposed to such a continuously changing environment. In this context, this paper addresses the protection challenges of the transmission system connecting with high wind penetration. This paper talks about distance relay performance when is used near to variable-speed doubly fed asynchronous (Type-3) wind turbine generators (WTGs). The present research work is done under WP4 of MIGRATE (Massive Integration of Power Electronic Devices) project [1],[2]. The power transmission network connected with Type-3 wind turbine generator has been developed in real-time digital power simulator (RTDS) environment in order to perform robust hardware in the loop test for two different vendor distance relay. The values of the distance relay settings are as per European Transmission System Operators (TSOs) setting criteria. This paper shows the conclusions and the results obtained in the tests applied to four different vendors (called in this document **A**, **B**, **C**, and **D**).

3. Distance protection behavior influenced by a PE based generators.

There are different factors that can compromise the behavior of the distance protection function in relays which are deployed near high power wind generator. Among others the unpredictable wind speed, type of wind generator, protection within the converters (chopper and crowbar), control strategy, and the fault characteristic. In this paper, only the last three factors are studied in bus connected to a Type-3 wind farm.

A. Types of Wind Generator

Wind farms use different types of generators, the most used are Type-3 and Type-4 wind farms. The electrical characteristics of the Type-3 are governed by interactions between a double feed induction machine and two voltage source converters (VSC). The rotor side is excited by the inverter which plays a role of AC source. Seen from the grid the dynamic behaviour of a Type-3 WTG, is led by the controller response rather than the physical characteristics of the machine. In a similar way, Type-4 based on permanent-magnet synchronous generators (PMSG) are completely decoupled to the grid by a back to back VSC which make the grid see this element as a power electronic device with fast transients. This contrast with traditional SG, where the behaviour is governed by the machine physics. As a consequence of the Power Electronic based (PE) wind turbine electrical characteristics, the short-circuit current amplitude and shape is different than traditional SG this is an important factor in a relay decision [3].

B. Crowbar and Chopper Protection

The grid code regulations regarding the fault ride through (FRT) [4], may cause damages to the converters, due to the current variation during faults when the WT is not allowed to be disconnected from the grid. To protect the converters, in Type-3 crowbar and chopper protections are used. Once they are activated they bypass the converters but the crowbar resistance offers different values of the fault current compared to the normal conditions for certain periods.

C. Control strategies

The control use in the back to back VSC which connect the DFIG rotor to the grid not only play a major role in order to obtain the maximum power and to maintain the stability of the WT but also change considerable the short-circuit current. There are different strategies to control the machine in this work the control use negative and positive currents in order to achieve the requirements by the Grid code [3] and to decrease the double frequency problem which may appear in the rotor.

D. Fault Characteristics

Fault location, fault resistance, mutual coupling and power swing, may affect the performance of the distance relay protection. Generally, a three phase (LLL) fault is more severe compared to single line to ground (SLG) fault the severity of this faults produce crowbar action. The combination of high crowbar resistance and rotor winding resistance makes it a high impedance fault which is very difficult for the protective relay to detect. In the other hand when an unbalance no grounded fault (LL) happen the control strategies follow by the VSC [5],[6] may deny negative sequence making the relay jeopardize and no trip.

4. Grid Model and Hardware in the Loop

In order to test the relays performance a grid model was developed in RSCAD software. The system is a 7buses, 4 generators network. Fig. 1. depicts the system, were a slack generator is connected at bus 0 and a HVDC link from bus 2 to 3. Two possibilities have been defined for the slack generator, strong network with high short-circuit power and weak network with low short-circuit power. The model was designed in a way that can include, in a straightforward manner, synchronous generators (SG) and/or renewables generators (RWG) at buses 5, 6, and 7. In this way, three main sceneries with different power level were studied (see TABLE I). In this paper the line from bus 1 to 4 (dashed line) were removed. Nevertheless it was used for diferent cases of study whitin the MIGRATE project [1].

According to the color code in Fig. 1, the main grid is a 400kV system while different voltage levels were used for the generators connected at buses 5, 6, and 7.

Fig. 1. Single line test system

This paper reports the performance of the relays covering the line from bus 4-6 where a Type-3 wind farm (DFIG) or synchronous generator (SG3) is connected through a 225MVA, 33kV-400kV, Δ transformer. In this place, the outgoing TL, from bus 4 to 6, is 30km length with positive and zero sequence impedances equal to $R_1 = 0.0293\Omega/km$, $XL_1 = 0.3087\Omega/km$, $XC_1 = 0.2664M\Omega/km$ and $R_0 = 0.3\Omega/km$, $XL_0 = 0.988\Omega/km$, $XC_0 = 0.4369M\Omega/km$. For faults at buses 5-7 and 5-4 please refer to [2], [7].

TABLE I
GENERATOR SCENARIOS

Scenery	Bus 5	Bus 6	Bus 7	Power level (MW per machine)
100% synchronous generators	SG1	SG3	SG2	40
				200
High Power Electronic based generators	PV	DFIG	PMSG	40
				200
Mixed scenario	SG1	DFIG	SG2	40
				200

A. DFIG control strategy.

The Type-3 wind farm model developed in RSCAD is an aggregate model which consists of a Double Feed Induction Generator (DFIG) which contains four inner controllers at grid and rotor Voltage Sources Converters (VSC). Two controllers regulate the positive sequence current components and the other two control the negative sequence ones. The positive sequence outer controllers in grid VSC are responsible to maintain constant the DC-link voltage and provide the required reactive power (as a STATCOM[6]) at the DFIG point of common coupling (PCC) based on the applied grid code. Simultaneously, the rotor VSC positive sequence outer controllers regulate the active and reactive power based on the optimal wind turbine power extraction and the applied grid code [8] respectively. Similar to the positive sequence controllers, four regulators are considered to control the negative sequence current components. Fig. 2 shows a general overview of the applied converter control schemes.

Fig. 2. DFIG inner and outer control strategy.

B. Hardware in the Loop.

As can be seen in Fig. 3 the HIL system is composed of a real-time simulator from RTDS, analogical/digital communication cards, two amplifiers, and four relays from two different manufacturers. This configuration was done in two different research centers, therefore four different relays manufactures were tested.

There are three types of signals used to exchange data between the RTS and relays: Analogical signals, currents and voltages are sending out RTS via analogical card (GTAO) the signals at this stage are voltages lower than 10V. These voltages are used to feed the amplifiers which recreate the secondary signals from the CTs and VTs used at each end of the protected line. Eight measured inputs must be available on the relays side: three phase to-earth voltages and one for the displacement voltage all of them from the VT and three phase and earth currents from the CT. Binary signals, trip (per phase) and reclosing (three phases) from the relays are collected in RTS by a digital card (GTDI). Binary high voltage signals (~110V) from the circuit breaker status are interchanged from RTDS to the relays by the high front panel (GTFPI). Closing the Loop in the hardware simulation.

Fig. 3. Hardware in the loop

5. Test scenarios

Based on the test system presented on Fig. 1, short circuit power, and types of generators on TABLE I, the variables involved in the tests are: Fault location: applied within zone 1, 2, and 3 (reverse, 0, 50, 70, 90, and 100% of the transmission line). Type of fault: single line-to-ground (SLG), line-to-line (LL),

line-to-line to ground (LLG) and three phase faults (LLL). A total of 240 different cases were simulated. Every case was repeated 3 times to confirm the proper relay behavior, hence 2880 results from the fourth relays were classified. Further details about test procedure and methodology can be found in [1],[2],[7].

6. Distance Protection Function Results

The Distance protection cases of studies were divided in 2. One with only SG in the system and the other where a PE-based renewable generator joined the system.

A. Synchronous generator scenery

Firstly to validate the relay setting provided by European Transmission System Operators (TSOs) the scenarios when only SG are in the system were simulated. It is worth to say that, the distance protection function was set with quadrilateral characteristic for SLG fault and Mho characteristic for other types of fault. Three protection zones were used: Zone 1 covering 85% of the line with an instantaneous trip time, Zone 2 covering 120% of the line with a 400ms trip time, and reverse Zone with 600ms trip time. The reconnection was not activated in Zone 2 and reverse. It is worth to say that only one set of relays deployed at bus 6 were used.

For all the SG scenarios the relays behavior were as expected; 98% of successful trips in corresponding zones. Fig. 4 shows some of the cases from (a) to (c) the inception fault was at 70% of the line for cases SLG, LL, and LLL. From (d) to (e) the fault inception was at 90% of the line. Average trips times are summarized in TABLE II. At the other end of the line the relays were disabled, simulating breaker failure at the remote position (bus 4).

TABLE II
RELAYS AVERAGE TRIP TIME

Zone	A	B	C	D
Z1	0.033s	0.023s	0.037s	0.021s
Z2	0.425s	0.422s	0.428s	0.419s

TABLE III
HIGH PE-BASED WT COMPARISON BETWEEN STRONG AND WEAK GRID.

Relay	Scenario	No trip (%)	Delayed trips (%)
	High PE-based penetration (DFIG, PMSG, PV)		
A	Strong	3.57	51.78
	Weak	6.54	50
B	Strong	19.64	36.3
	Weak	22.61	29.7
C	Strong	11.30	30.4
	Weak	11.90	30.4
D	Strong	21.42	32.1
	Weak	23.8	29.1

Fig. 4. Voltages, currents and impedance trajectories during faults in a 100% 40MW SGs, weak grid, scenarios with faults inceptions at: (a) 70% line SLG, (b) 70% line LL, (c) 70% line LLL (d) 90% line SLG, (e) 90% line LL, (f) 90% line LLL.

A. Power electronic based generator scenario

In this case SG1, SG2, and SG3 at buses 5, 6, and 7 were replaced by Photovoltaic, Type-3 and Type-4 wind turbines. The scenarios of weak/strong and 40MW/200MW remains unchanged as well the type and fault inception.

For each relay the results disclose that there are no significant differences between weak and strong grid conditions in terms of no trip and delayed cases. However, the performance of each manufacturer is different due to the relay algorithm inside the product. Fig. 5 (A), (B), (C), and (D) show the results for all type of scenarios classified for relay and type of fault.

More than the number of faults where the protection relays present an unexpected behavior, it is interesting to see the distribution of the bar chart for the different manufacturers. It is a matter of fact

Fig. 5. Percentage of missed per type of fault and manufacturer in a high PE-based scenario

that the general theory of distance protection is based on impedance measurement. However, in this analysis of results, clearly different behaviors can be observed for the different protection manufacturers for type of fault. At this moment, it is interesting to remind that the voltage and current signals that protection relays see is the same for the four vendors, thanks to the use of the same

Fig. 6. Bus 6 signals during a SLG fault 70% of the line, scenario high PE-based generators weak grid: (a) Voltages, currents and relay commands, (b) current reference signals at the GSC, (c) voltage drop vs grid code limits, and (d) impedance trajectory

Fig. 7. Bus 6 signals during a LL fault 70% of the line, scenario high PE-based generators weak grid: (a) Voltages, currents and relay commands, (b) current reference signals at the GSC, (c) voltage drop vs grid code limits, and (d) impedance trajectory

RTDS model and same script files in both laboratories.

From Fig. 5, it can be seen that the protection fails mainly during LL and LLL faults in a infeed from the DFIG.

Three cases in high PE-based generators scenario were selected to show in this paper. On Fig. 6 a SLG fault is show. In this case, there is no issue with the relay behavior. Nevertheless, there is a quarter cycle delay in trip time in comparison with the SG cases. The average relays trip times were $\mathbf{A}=0.037\text{s}$, $\mathbf{B}=0.027\text{s}$, $\mathbf{C}=0.038$, and $\mathbf{D}=0.028$ for fault inception at 70% of the line. The control references at the Grid Side Converter (GSC) seen in Fig. 6 (b), present an expected behavior. During pre-fault condition only i_d^+ reference is necessary to control the VSC grid side, then during fault-state negative references are necessary (i_q^-) [9]. If the voltage drops more than 10% the PCC voltage (according with Tennet grid code [4]) the i_d^+ and i_d^- must be activate and support the grid with reactive power. In Fig. 6 (c) the red dashed lines enclose the zone were voltage support is not necessary (Voltage support limit 1 and 2). The voltage support can be provide as long the current trough the converters do not overcome the threshold (1.2pu) used to prevent damage in the VSC. Fig. 6 (d) shows the impedance trajectory in quadrilateral shape. For SLG faults with any scenario the relays the detected fault inside the correct protection zones.

Fig. 7 shows a LL fault at 70% of the line in a weak system case. In this case the relays fails to produce the trip command. It has been observed that the impedance calculation is performed by the protection and its value reach the Zone 1. Impedance trajectory reach the corresponding zone although there is not trip action. During this cases, after the fault inception the control is loss for some milliseconds because the current trough the VSC exceeds its limit. The loss of control produce distortions in the current and voltage shapes.

A LLL fault at 70% of the line is shown in Fig. 8 In this case the LVRT (Low Voltage Ride Through) was disable in order to see the behavior of the Type-3 wind turbine during one second fault. For this cases the impedance trajectory find stop in the corresponding zone. Nevertheless, there is not trip action. The control reference i_d^+ reach its limit to support the system. In this case of balanced fault the main control is implemented in the positive frame. On reference signals shown in Fig. 8 (d) it can be

Fig. 8. Bus 6 signals during a LLL fault 70% of the line, scenario high PE-based generators weak grid: (a) Voltages, currents and relay commands, (b) current reference signals at the GSC, (c) voltage drop vs grid code limits, and (d) impedance trajectory

seen some negative current control just after the fault, this current reference is immediately regulated and decrease leaving the control to the positive frame. The wind turbine does not lose the stability.

The electrical signals shown at Fig. 6, Fig. 7, and Fig. 8 disclose the correct operation of the DFIG control during pre-fault and fault condition, particularly:

- Positive and negative sequence controls: for rotor side converter, to eliminate the torque oscillations at double supply frequency under unbalance voltage and GSC to cancel the oscillation by active power[10].
- Current limitation in converters by the use of chopper and crowbar circuits and controls.

According to the grid code, when the fault current occurs and voltage drops more than allowed (the size of voltage dip depends on the fault type), a reactive current is injected in order to support and recover the voltage. This voltage recovery is important for the fault detection as lower voltage and a low fault current may result in failure of the starting element to detect the fault. Hence trip signal may not be given. A fault may also not be detected when the fault current amplitude significantly drops within one or two cycles not providing an opportunity to detect the amplitude change by a specific starter element (which was not the case in present situation).

It depends on the manufacturer the starting point (Pick up) of the fault. Some used algorithms may be delta algorithm, under impedance starting, over-current starting, U/I/phase starting, etc.

In all cases It can be seen that the impedance approaches gradually, during relay tripping (Fig. 6 (d)) or abruptly, during relay failure (Fig. 7 (d)). In case of protection tripping, relay operation time may be delayed because of the reactive current injection needed to recover voltage and hence detect the fault. This may also result in relay under reach.

7. Conclusions

Distance protection function in four different manufacturers relays has been tested in a HiL using RTDS.

Large DFIG-based wind farms have the potential to adversely affect the existing generator distance protection relays. Such an effect varies with the wind farm rating and location, fault type, fault location self-protection and control strategy.

During LL and LLL faults, the occurrence of the fault activates the DFIG-based wind farm grid and rotor-side converters protection system, which causes the crowbar control bypass the converter and short-circuit the rotor windings. As a result, the DFIG-based wind farm operates as an induction generator and starts absorbing large amount of reactive power from the system.

The presence of DFIG-based wind farms and its contribution to the fault current during system faults changes the measured impedance of relay. This is due to the changes in both the voltages and currents measured by the relay elements. Moreover, these changes in the measured impedance vary with the fault type, fault location and generator loading. During faults, reactive current injection takes place in order to recover the voltage according to the grid code. Failure to recover the voltage results in relay failure to detect the fault and not providing a trip signal even though the impedance is in the tripping zone.

The accuracy of the simulated fault currents has been verified by waveforms of so far provided measurements from laboratory and field tests. The failure of protection to operate on similar cases was so far elaborated in some publications [11], [12] however, no explanation was provided on the reasons and origin of this problem. The results can be used as indication of possible bottlenecks of the currently available protection schemes.

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9. Disclaimer

This paper reflects only the MIGRATE consortium views and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

10. References

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